

A new Reagent *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl Sulphonamido) Aniline for Spectrophotometric Determination of Cerium (IV)

Wahid U. Malik and T. C. Sharma

The red coloured complex formed by cerium (iv), with *o*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline, forms the basis of a very sensitive colorimetric method for the determination of traces of the metal. The complex shows maximum absorbance at 480 $m\mu$ where the reagent has negligible absorption. Many cations and anions are without effect on the complex. A composition study by various usual methods shows that 1 : 2 complex formed.

The spectrophotometric determination of Cerium(IV) has not hitherto received much attention and few organic reagents have been employed for this purpose¹⁻⁵. *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline has been extensively studied in these laboratories as a chelating reagent. Billman *et al.*⁶ used *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl sulphonamido) aniline as an analytical reagent and found that it formed deeply coloured complexes with Copper(II) in the presence of pyridine. In our earlier communication⁷ we have reported that the reagent can be utilised even in the absence of pyridine for the determination of Copper(II) in alcoholic medium. It has now been found that when alcoholic solution of this reagent is treated with Cerium salt solution, a reddish, brown complex is obtained. The complex is stable and obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 480 $m\mu$ in the concentration range 2 to 20 p.p.m. of Cerium.

EXPERIMENTAL

O-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline was prepared by the following process :

5 gm *o*-Phenylendiamine was placed in 100 ml. three necked flask and dissolved in 30 ml. pyridine. The flask was fitted with a motor stirrer and immersed in an ice bath. 9 gms. of *p*-toluene sulphonylchloride was added to the above solution in small quantity over a 2 hrs. period and the solution being stirred throughout. The reaction mixture is then poured into 60 ml. of cold water with vigorous stirring. A black oil settles at the bottom and the supernatant liquid is decanted. The oil is taken up in 50 : 50 mixture of 95% ethyl alcohol-water, heated and norited. The solution is allowed to cool and then the desired

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product was crystallized out. It is recrystallized from 50 to 50 ethyl-alcohol-water, yielding a white flufy compound (yield 8.9 gm, 80%, melting point 135° (lit.) observed $135-136^{\circ}$). An ethanol solution of the order 10^{-3} mole/litre of the purified reagent was used. The standard cerium solution was made from cerium sulphate (A.R.) in $0.1N$ H_2SO_4 . All other reagents employed were of A.R. grade. The solutions were stored in a refrigerator.

Absorbance were measured with a Bousch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. pH measurements were made with a Phillips pH meter model no H.

RESULTS

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectrum of *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline showed no maximum in alcoholic medium. The absorbance spectrum of the Cerium—*O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline complex showed a maximum at $480 m\mu$. The absorption due to the reagent-cerium complex at this wave length was quite appreciable. All subsequent studies of the complex were carried out at $480 m\mu$. The optical density at $480 m\mu$ of a series of solutions containing the reagent and Cerium(IV) in molar ratios were determined. The results (Fig. 1) show that the optical density increases linearly to the molar ratio of 5. During subsequent estimations of the molar ratio of the reagent to Cerium was maintained at 10. An excess of the reagent affects the optical density of the complex.

FIG 1

Stability of the complex : The colour of the complex appeared after half an hour of mixing the two reactants. The colour of the complex was found to be stable for 3 days or more, but complex was found to obey Lambert-Beer's law at $480 m\mu$ for 20 hr. only.

Nature of complexes : The nature of the complex formed in solution was determined by employing Job's method of continuous variations, as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper^{8,9,10}. Mixtures of the metal salts and *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline with varying metal : ligand ratio were prepared. The absorbance of each mixture were measured at $480 m\mu$ (Fig. II).

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The molar composition of the Cerium complex was also verified by the slope ratio method¹¹. For this purpose two series of solutions were prepared. In one series the

FIG II

Cerium(IV) concentration was varied maintaining the concentration of the *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline constant and in sufficient excess. In the other, *O*-(*p*-Toluyyl-sulphonamido) aniline concentration was varied, maintaining the concentration of Cerium (IV) constant and in sufficient excess. The absorbance of the solutions of both these series were determined at 480 mμ taking alcohol as reference. In the curves only the straight line portions were taken into account to find out the slopes.

The results obtained by slope ratio, molar ratio and Job's continuous variation method indicate that the molar ratio of the ligand to Cerium(IV) in the complex is 2 : 1.

Effect of the diverse ions : The effect of several ions on the colour complex was studied and was found that Ce(III) and Cu(II) interfere at all concentrations. Other ions i.e., acetate, halides, citrates, phosphates, tartarates Ti(IV), Hf(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV), Mo(VI), Cr(III), Mn(II), Pt(IV) etc., must not increase 200 p.p.m.

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Chemistry Department,
University of Roorkee,
Roorkee.

and
Chemistry Department,
College of Science,
Gurukul Kangri.

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